

BIOTIC INTERFERENCE AND BIODIVERSITY LOSS IN DHULE AND NANDURBAR DISTRICTS (MAHARASHTRA: INDIA): A REVIEW

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Abstract

The erstwhile Dhule district is presently divided into two districts viz., Dhule and Nandurbar in Maharashtra state (India). The ethnobotanical observations during botanization in the region yielded noteworthy information on local biodiversity. As many as 34 plant species pertaining to 28 genera and 21 angiospermic families appeared under exploitation. These are being used tremendously for various purposes. Their underground parts, leaves, flowers, fruits, seeds or entire plants are being exhausted for daily human needs in these districts. Their use-reports are analysed as such: underground parts (08), leaves (05), flowers (02), fruits (07), seeds (03), entire plants (01), fibre (01), for fodder (03) and timber (07). The figures in parenthesis denoted for number of species. If this trend of over-exploitation is not checked in time, these taxa may deplete further in nature. Thought of sustainability was inherent in Indian culture but with time, human population is forced towards over-exploitation for various reasons. An awareness of native people is the need of hour to save biodiversity loss in these districts.

Keywords: *Biotic Interference, Biodiversity, Ethnobotany, Dhule-Nandurbar Districts.*

Introduction:

The erstwhile Dhule district is divided into two districts viz., Dhule and Nandurbar. It stretches between 73°47' and 75°11' east longitudes and 20°38' and 22°3' north latitudes. It is bounded on the north by Gujarat and Madhya Pradesh state. The Jalgaon and Nasik districts limit it on the east and south respectively. It comprises 10 revenue tehsils. The forests area is located mainly in the ranges of Satpura mountain separating on north from Gujarat and Madhya Pradesh states of India. It lies in Tapi valley. The forests in the region

are tropical, dry deciduous type. The vegetation varies with the changes in altitude, aspects and rainfall. It is inhabited by non-tribal agrarian population, apart from tribes such as Bhils, Pawara, Mavachi, Kokani etc. The tribes partially depend on forest products.

Methodology:

The said region is botanized floristically by the present author (Patil, 2003). During these visits special care was also undertaken to note traditional uses especially by the tribal people who depend on forests for their daily life necessities. Information was obtained with respect to vernacular plant name, part used and purpose of use (medicinal and non-medicinal). The plant determination was completed by consulting the floras viz., (i) Cooke (1958), Sharma *et al.* (1996), Singh *et al.* (2000, 2001). The severity of biotic interference particularly about wild plant species on account of traditional practices was carefully recorded during field work. The information so gathered is dilated in this communication.

Systematic Enumeration:

I. Underground Parts:

1.	<i>Sterculia urens</i> Roxb. (Sterculiaceae) Kadai, Kewdi Use: Young roots of saplings after removal of bark are eaten raw.
2.	<i>Pueraria tuberosa</i> (Roxb. ex Willd.) DC. (Papilionaceae) Bendra, Shirwala Use: Tubers are consumed
3.	<i>Engete superbum</i> (Roxb.) Cheesm. (Musaceae) Use: Rhizome is consumed.
4.	<i>Dioscorea belophylla</i> (Prain) Haines (Dioscoreaceae) Kadua-Kand. Use: Tubers are boiled and consumed.
5.	<i>Dioscorea bulbifera</i> L. (Dioscoreaceae) Kand Use: Tubers and bulbils are consumed.
6.	<i>Chlorophytum borivilianum</i> (Thunb.) Jacq. (Liliaceae) Safed-musale, Sabuk-musali Use: Tubers are consumed raw.
7.	<i>Milletia extensa</i> (Benth) Hooker (Papilionaceae) Agari, Paladi Use: Roots are used for fish-killing.
8.	<i>Balanites aegyptica</i> (L.) Del. (Balanitaceae) Hinganbet, Hingornya Use: Roots are used for fish-killing

II. Leaves:

1.	<i>Diospyros melanoxylon</i> Roxb. (Ebenaceae) Termu, Tendu, Temburni Use: Leaves are used for bidi-wrapping and sold in markets.
2.	<i>Schrebera swietenoides</i> Roxb. (Oleaceae) Mokha, Tikha-al Use: Leaves are used as vegetable.
3.	<i>Rivea hypocrateriformis</i> (Desr.) Choisy (Convolvulaceae) Fang Use: Leaves are used for vegetable purpose.
4.	<i>Chlorophytum borivilianum</i> (Thunb.) Jacq. (Liliaceae) Safed-musali, Sabuk0musali Use: Leaves are used as vegetable.
5.	<i>Chlorophytum tuberosum</i> (Roxb.) Baker (Liliaceae) Ran-ratalu, Dombali Use: Leaves are used as vegetable.

III. Flowers:

1.	<i>Ensete superbum</i> (Roxb.) Cheesm. (Musaceae) Lathada, Chivani Use: Inflorescence axis is used as vegetable.
2.	<i>Holostemma ada-kodien</i> Schult. (Asclepiadaceae) Shiri, Shiriful, Safed-shiri Use: Flowers are consumed raw

IV. Fruits:

1.	<i>Capparis zeylanica</i> L. (Capparadaceae) Wagati Use: Fruit wall is used as vegetable.
2.	<i>Ziziphus rugosa</i> Lamk. (Rhamnaceae) Toran, Tora Use: Ripe fruit are consumed.
3.	<i>Leea asiatica</i> (L.) Ridsdale (Leeaceae) Lahan-deni Use: Fruits are consumed.
4.	<i>Rhus sinuata</i> Thunb. (Anacardiaceae) Amoni Use: Unripe fruits are sour and edible. They are sold near schools.
5.	<i>Meyna laxiflora</i> Robyns (Rubiaceae) Aliv, Ulama Use: Ripe fruits are consumed.
6.	<i>Dendrophthoe falcata</i> (L.f.) Etting. (Loranthaceae) Munda, Lephade, Bendguli Use: Ripe fruits are cherished.
7.	<i>Balanites aegyptiaca</i> (L.) Del. (Balanitaceae) Hinganbet, Higonrnya Use: Fruits are used for washing clothes.

V. Seeds:

1.	<i>Sterculia urens</i> Roxb. (Sterculiaceae) Kadai, Kewdi Use: Seeds after de-coating are consumed raw.
2.	<i>Holoptelea integrifolia</i> (Roxb.) Planch (Ulmaceae) Papada, Sanjari Use: Seeds are consumed.
3.	<i>Pentatropis spiralis</i> (Forsk.) Decne. (Asclepiadaceae) Popti-Sheg Use: Young seeds consumed raw.

VI. Entire Plants:

1.	<i>Caralluma adscendens</i> (Roxb.) R.Br. (Asclepiadaceae) Vanjari-bhaji Use: Entire plants are used as vegetable.
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VII. Fibre:

1.	<i>Helicteres isora</i> L. (Sterculiaceae) Murud-shebg, Attadi, Atti Use: Fruits ribbons are removed from entire stem-axes and use for hut construction.
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VIII. Fodder:

1.	<i>Grewia tillifolia</i> Vahl (Tiliaceae) Rodgi, Dhaman Use: Leaves fed to goats.
2.	<i>Ougeinia oojeinensis</i> (Roxb.) Hochr. (Papilionaceae) Tiwas, Tinis Use: Young shoots are used as fodder for cattle.
3.	<i>Hardwickia binata</i> Roxb. (Caesalpiniaceae) Anjan Use: Leaves are used as fodder for cattle.

IX. Timber:

1.	<i>Ougeinia oojeinensis</i> (Roxb.) Hochr. (Papilionaceae) Tiwas, Tinis Use: Wood is used for bullock-carts.
2.	<i>Hardwickia binata</i> Roxb. (Caesalpiniaceae) Anjan Use: Wood is used for agricultural implements.
3.	<i>Anogeissus latifolia</i> (Roxb. ex DC.) Wall ex Guill. (Lythraceae) Dwada, Dhamdo Use: Wood is used as pillars of huts.
4.	<i>Lagerstroemia parviflora</i> Roxb. (Lythraceae) Bondara Use: Wood is used for constructing huts.
5.	<i>Haldina cordifolia</i> (Roxb.) Ridsd. (Rubiaceae) Haladu, Haldanu Use: Wood is used for huts and houses.
6.	<i>Mallotus philippensis</i> (Lamk.) Muell.-Arg. (Euphorbiaceae) Shendry, Hendra Use: Wood is used for hut construction.

7.	<i>Terminalia cuneata</i> Roth (Combretaceae) Arjun-Sadada [Syn. <i>T.arjuna</i> (Roxb.) Wight & Arn.] Use: Wood is used for house-construction.
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Results And Discussion:

The erstwhile Dhule district (presently divided into Dhule and Nandurbar districts) is dominated by tribal population such as Bhils, Pawara, Mavahi, Kokani, Kokana, etc. Major livelihood is although agriculture, still they depend partially on forest species for their necessities of life. The ranges Satpura mountain extend on its north-western side. These districts are botanized floristically intensively (Patil, 2003). During this investigation observations on plant utilities by the local inhabitants have been carefully recorded alongwith their occurrence, distribution, phenology and indigenous utilities. This attempt takes into consideration especially indigenous wild species which are suffering from severe biotic interference.

Local inhabitants use various plant parts or even entire plants for their necessities of life. During period of botanisation, the underground, parts e.g. young shoots of saplings, rhizomes, tubers and roots were found employed for different purposes. Total 08 species pertaining to 07 genera and 06 families are exploited for their underground parts from wild populations. They consumed them either raw or cooked. Two species viz., *Milletia extensa* (Benth.) Hooker and *Balanites aegyptiaca* (L.) Del. are utilized for fish killing. While using the roots of former, entire plants are rooted out and the aerial parts thrown and wasted. In latter case, the seeds are not dispersed naturally in their native habitats. All these are destructive practices prevailing in the district. Consequently, few plants are surviving in their home.

Foliage is important part of the plants since they produce nutrients needed for them. These are collected in large quantities. Total 05 species belonging to 04 species and 04 families are extensively exploited mostly for vegetable. Leaves of *Diospyros melanoxylon* (Roxb.) are collected on large scale for bidi-wrapping. This trend has diminishing effects on their live populations in the district.

Flowers obviously constitute essential parts in view of reproduction in plants. Flowers are consumed raw or the inflorescence axis is used for vegetable purpose. In the latter case, viz., *Ensete superbum* entire plant is spoiled while removing the useful part. Moreover, its rhizome is also unearthed being edible. Total two species are being depleted because of this

traditional practice. Fruits are also similarly exploited for vegetable and washing clothes. Some ripe fruits are cherished. As many as 07 species belonging to 07 genera and 07 families which grow in wild are utilized on large scale. This traditional practice reduces the chances of natural fruit dispersal and thereby minimize these taxa in wild. The case of seed is not again different from those of fruits. Total 03 species belonging to 03 genera and 03 families are utilized for their seeds. Seeds are consumed raw. The case of *Caralluma adscendens* (Roxb.) R. Br. is more precarious. The plants are branched, fleshy and succulent but bears no leaves. These are used as vegetable. Entire plants are removed and there is no possibility of their regeneration or dispersal in nature. It is observed that fibrous bark is removed from stems of *Helicteres isora*. Its ribbons are used during but construction. This practice aids in destruction of entire plants.

The tribal and non-tribal people rear domestic animals. They collect leaves on large scale from 03 species belonging to 03 genera and 03 families which are wild in nature. This practice also has deleterious effect on the populations of these taxa. Timber is needed for huts, houses and sheds for cattle. Entire trees are cut down. As many as 07 tree species belonging to 07 genera and 07 families are commonly employed for the said purpose. This trend has reduced their number in forested areas. Obviously, dispersal of fruits and seeds is affected and thereby minimized their population in nature. Some weeds in waste lands exotic herbaceous flora as agricultural weeds are also used for various purposes. They are but quite aggressive and invasive and can maintain their own populations.

In a nutshell, over-exploitation of various plants, use of entire plants or cutting down entire trees are responsible for denuding the forests. These, in near future, may be threatened and even depleted for ever from the natural scenario.

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